

Conductivity of Strong Electrolytes in Aqueous Organic Solvents

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The conductivity values of electrolytes in aqueous organic solvents decrease continuously with the increasing organic solvent content. The ionic conductivities are proportional to N^2 (N being number of solvent moles in the mixture), for example (1) of H^+ and OH^- in all compositions of four aqueous organic solvents, (2) of Na^+ , K^+ and Cl^- in all compositions of water-ethanol and water-dioxane and (3) of Na^+ , K^+ and Cl^- up to 50 : 50 composition of water-methanol and water-acetone remaining constant in low water mixtures. The proportionality is due (a) to the structural similarity of aqueous organic solvents, (b) to the dielectric behaviour because of the preponderance of water molecules in the solvation sheath around the ions and (c) to the absence of resistance of the polymeric species in aqueous organic solvents to the passage of the ions.

ALTHOUGH considerable work has been reported on measurements of conductivity of various electrolytes in aqueous organic solvents, the relationship between conductivity and solvent composition is not well understood. The different systems reported in literature are (1) sulphuric acid in water-ethanol^{1, 2}, (2) hydrochloric acid, nitric acid and sulphuric acid in water-methanol, water-ethanol, water-acetone and water-dioxane³, (3) salts in water-acetone^{4, 5}, (4) hydrogen chloride and potassium chloride in water-acetone⁶, (5) salts in water-dioxane⁷ and (6) others⁸.

Among various explanations given for the abnormal conductance in mixed solvents are (1) sulphuric acid exists as hydrate, $H_2SO_4 \cdot H_2O$, (2) sulphuric acid distributes itself between the two solvents, the association between solvent molecules and ions depending on the molar composition³ and (3) equivalent conductivity is not only dependent on viscosity of solvent mixture but also is affected by dielectric constant of the mixed solvent⁶.

It is evident that electrical conductivity of electrolytes in mixed solvent is influenced firstly by the concentration of electrolyte and secondly by the viscosity of solvent medium. Relationships between viscosity and solvent composition in terms of nature and number of solvent moles in the mixture have been separately discussed^{9, 10}. This paper deals with the correlation between the conductivity of certain strong electrolytes in aqueous organic solvents and the solvent composition.

Materials and Methods

AnalaR grade chemicals were used. The conductivity water having conductivity of 3.9×10^{-6}

ohms was obtained by passing double distilled water through a mixed bed ion exchange column. The organic solvents were carefully purified before use¹¹⁻¹³. The purity was confirmed by determining boiling point, density and refractive index^{14, 15}.

To prepare the solutions of electrolytes, first 10 ml of aqueous solution was taken in a volumetric flask and the organic solvent was added to it to make up 100 ml volume. As some rise in temperature took place, the flask was cooled to 30°.

Measurements were made with nine compositions of each system at equal intervals of 10 ml and three more intermediate compositions. Corning glass apparatus with the usual precautions was used.

Specific conductivities were determined using 25 ml solution in a conductometer of Wheatstone bridge type with magic eye indicator accurate to 2 percent and dipping type cell (cell constant 0.859) with freshly platinised electrode. The solution with the cell was thermostated at 30° in a water thermostat precise to $\pm 0.1^\circ$ for 20 minutes before the conductivity determination.

Results

The results of determination of equivalent conductivity of 0.005M each of potassium chloride, sodium chloride, sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid in four aqueous organic solvent systems namely water-methanol, water-ethanol, water-acetone and water-dioxane at 30° are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

The equivalent conductivity values of the four electrolytes decrease continuously with the increasing

TABLE 1—EQUIVALENT CONDUCTIVITIES OF SODIUM AND POTASSIUM CHLORIDES IN AQUEOUS ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT 30°

Water in Mixed Solvent % by Volume	Equivalent Conductivity of 0.005M in Aqueous Organic Solvent of							
	Sodium Chloride				Potassium Chloride			
	W + E	W + M	W + A	W + D	W + E	W + M	W + A	W + D
100	123.7	123.7	123.7	123.7	145.2	145.2	145.2	145.2
97.5	116.0	116.8	120.3	116.8	142.3	140.0	144.0	144.3
95	111.7	114.3	116.9	113.4	137.4	135.7	143.5	139.2
92.5	106.5	108.2	113.4	104.8	125.4	130.6	138.3	130.6
90	94.5	104.7	110.8	103.1	117.7	125.4	130.6	125.4
80	81.6	89.3	94.5	95.4	91.1	108.2	113.4	104.8
70	64.4	85.0	85.9	85.9	82.5	98.6	99.6	94.5
60	54.1	78.2	82.5	70.4	63.6	86.8	90.2	68.8
50	48.1	73.9	73.9	59.3	60.1	84.2	85.9	60.1
40	47.3	67.0	68.7	48.0	49.8	81.6	84.2	46.4
30	43.0	63.6	64.4	30.1	47.3	80.8	79.0	33.5
20	37.8	67.0	64.4	13.6	41.2	79.9	76.5	14.1
10	32.6	72.2	64.4	11.3	37.8	84.2	73.0	11.6
5	—	—	50.7	—	—	—	—	—

Note : W, E, M, A, D stand for Water, Ethanol, Methanol, Acetone and Dioxane respectively.

TABLE 2—EQUIVALENT CONDUCTIVITIES OF SODIUM HYDROXIDE AND HYDROCHLORIC ACID IN AQUEOUS ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT 30°

Water in Mixed Solvent % by Volume	Equivalent Conductivity of 0.005M in Aqueous Organic Solvent of							
	Sodium Hydroxide				Hydrochloric Acid			
	W + E	W + M	W + A	W + D	W + E	W + M	W + A	W + D
100	253.4	253.4	253.4	253.4	420.9	420.9	420.9	420.9
97.5	213.3	212.2	237.6	229.8	390.9	408.9	395.1	414.4
95	203.6	201.9	226.8	219.0	384.8	389.1	386.5	405.5
92.5	192.4	189.0	207.9	213.2	352.2	369.4	371.1	382.5
90	182.1	181.3	201.9	183.8	343.6	356.3	365.1	379.2
80	150.3	147.8	163.2	142.2	283.5	307.4	309.2	323.3
70	116.0	120.3	137.4	100.6	210.5	257.7	262.0	257.5
60	85.9	108.2	111.7	74.6	170.1	211.3	227.6	173.3
50	84.2	91.9	90.2	53.4	134.4	180.4	182.1	131.4
40	66.1	85.9	77.8	35.4	110.8	146.0	154.6	101.8
30	53.3	81.6	64.4	23.2	85.9	123.7	116.8	76.8
20	43.0	77.3	47.3	9.4	64.4	91.9	90.1	28.3
10	34.0	79.0	24.9	0.6	43.0	90.2	53.3	1.5
5	—	—	8.6	—	—	—	25.8	—

Note : W, E, M, A, D, stand for Water, Ethanol, Methanol, Acetone and Dioxane respectively.

organic solvent content in the mixed solvent. Whereas in water-ethanol and water-dioxane, the drop in the conductivity values goes on from 90 : 10 to 10 : 90 compositions steadily, the drop in the case of water-methanol and water-acetone is continuous up to 50 : 50 composition and subsequent changes in the conductivity values are negligible.

In the case of both sodium and potassium chlorides, conductivity values in (1) water-ethanol and water-dioxane are similar up to 50 : 50 composition and the water-ethanol values are higher than the water-dioxane values, (2) water-acetone and water-methanol values are identical at 50 : 50 composition and water-acetone value is slightly

lower than that in water-methanol at 10 : 90 composition, (3) the conductivities of potassium chloride and sodium chloride at all concentrations in all the systems maintain the order $KCl > NaCl$ and (4) the order in which conductivity values vary in four aqueous organic solvents is water-methanol > water-acetone > water-ethanol > water-dioxane for both sodium and potassium chlorides.

The numerical values of conductivity of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid indicate that up to 50 : 50 composition of water-ethanol and water-dioxane, conductivities of the two electrolytes are similar and in high organic solvent mixtures the drop of conductivity in the case of water-dioxane mixture

is more than in water-ethanol. In fact in 10 : 90 composition, the conductivity values of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid in water-dioxane are almost nil. It is noteworthy that at 10 : 90 composition, the conductivity value of hydrochloric acid is similar to those of alkali metal chlorides in water-ethanol but the former is less than the latter in water-dioxane systems. The conductivity values of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid in water-methanol and water-acetone point out to the identical behaviour of the two electrolytes in water-methanol and water-acetone up to 50 : 50 composition but different behaviour after that composition. As a result of these peculiarities in the behaviour in different solvent systems, the conductivity of hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide in 10 : 90 composition is maximum in water-methanol and minimum in water-dioxane, the order being water-methanol > water-acetone > water-ethanol > water-dioxane for hydrochloric acid and water-methanol > water-ethanol > water-acetone > water-dioxane for sodium hydroxide.

The values of ion conductances at 30° in water organic solvent mixtures are not available in literature. The values for highly solvated ions viz. Na^+ , K^+ and Cl^- are calculated by dividing the equivalent conductivity of electrolytes at 30° in the ratio of the ionic conductances of the constituent ions in aqueous medium. First ionic conductances of sodium, potassium and chloride ions are calculated from the equivalent conductivity of sodium chloride and potassium chloride employing the limiting transport number values in aqueous medium 0.3961, 0.4904 and 0.5095 for sodium, potassium and chloride ions respectively^{1,6}. The values of the ionic conductivity of chloride ions obtained from the equivalent conductivity magnitudes of sodium chloride and potassium chloride agree among themselves. The ionic conductivity of the less solvated ions (H^+ , OH^-) is determined indirectly, for example ionic conductivity of hydrogen ions is calculated by deducting the ionic conductivity of chloride ion calculated from the experimentally observed equivalent conductivity value for hydrochloric acid and the ionic conductivity of hydroxyl ion is calculated by deducting the ionic conductivity of sodium ion from the equivalent conductivity of sodium hydroxide. The relationships between ionic conductivities in different aqueous organic solvents and N^2 , N being total number of solvent moles per litre of solution are graphically shown in Figs. 1 to 5.

Hydrogen Ion :

The relationship between equivalent conductivity of hydrogen ion and N^2 is linear in all the four aqueous organic solvent systems. It is seen that the relationship is closely observed in water-acetone. The agreement with the relationship is good in water-dioxane. But in aqueous alcohols, the equivalent conductivity of hydrogen ion is somewhat lower than the value calculated according to

the relationship. The equivalent conductivity of hydrogen in aqueous methanol is slightly higher than in aqueous ethanol. At 50 : 50 composition, equivalent conductivity values of hydrogen ion in water-methanol 137.5 and water-acetone 138.3 are identical, somewhat lower in water-ethanol 104.4 and water-dioxane 100.8, but agreeing with each other. At 10 : 90 composition, the values are water-methanol 47.3, water-ethanol 23.7, water-acetone 16.4 and water-dioxane nil (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 : Plot of Equivalent Conductivity of Hydrogen Ion against Square of Number of Moles in one Litre of Aqueous Organic Solvent : (1) aqueous acetone (O), (2) aqueous dioxane (X), (3) aqueous ethanol (Δ), and (4) aqueous methanol (\bullet).

Hydroxyl Ion :

The relationship between the equivalent conductivity of hydroxyl ion and N^2 is linear. The agreement is not as good as in the case of hydrogen ion but the values are closer to the expected values in water-acetone medium. At 50 : 50 composition, the equivalent conductivity values for water-acetone 60.9, water-methanol 65.3 and water-ethanol 64.5 agree among themselves but the value is low in water-dioxane 32.3. In 10 : 90 composition, the

values are water-acetone, nil, water-dioxane nil, water-ethanol 20.6 and water-methanol 48 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Plot of Equivalent Conductivity of Hydroxyl Ion against Square of Number of Moles in one litre of Aqueous Organic Solvent: (1) aqueous acetone (O), (2) aqueous dioxane (X), (3) aqueous ethanol (Δ), and (4) aqueous methanol (\bullet).

Sodium, Potassium and Chloride Ions :

At 50 : 50 composition, the equivalent conductivity values of sodium ion are identical in water-methanol and water-acetone namely 29.3, somewhat lower but almost identical in water-ethanol and water-dioxane namely 19.1 and 21.1 respectively. At 10 : 90 composition, the values are 28.6 (water-methanol), 12.9 (water-ethanol), 25.5 (water-acetone) and 4.5 (water-dioxane) (Fig. 3).

Equivalent conductivity values of potassium ion are in water-methanol 41.3, water-acetone 42.1, water-ethanol 29.5 and water-dioxane 29.5 at 50 : 50 composition. These values are identical for water-methanol and water-acetone but somewhat lower and agreeing with each other for water-ethanol and water-dioxane. At 10 : 90 composition, the values are water-methanol 39.2, water-acetone 36.1, water-ethanol 18.5 and water-dioxane 5.7 (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3: Plot of Equivalent Conductivity of Sodium Ion against Square of Number of Moles in one litre of Aqueous Organic Solvent: (1) aqueous acetone (O), (2) aqueous dioxane (X), (3) aqueous ethanol (Δ), and (4) aqueous methanol (\bullet).

Behaviour is similar for the chloride ion. At 50 : 50 composition the conductivity values are for water-ethanol 30.6, water-methanol 42.9, water-acetone 43.8 and water-dioxane 30.6. The corresponding values at 10 : 90 composition are 19.2, 40.7, nil, 5.9 respectively (Fig. 5).

Equivalent conductivity curves for these ions thus are similar for (a) water-acetone and water-methanol and (b) water-ethanol and water-dioxane. The curves for water-acetone and water-methanol show regular decrease upto 50 : 50 composition and then the values are constant in low water mixtures. On the other hand, in water-dioxane and water-ethanol media, the conductivity values show linear relationship and diminish even after 50 : 50 composition.

Discussion

The liquid water is composed of octamers and dimers^{9,10}. In a mixture of water and organic solvent, owing to the interaction between water and organic

Fig. 4 : Plot of Equivalent Conductivity of Potassium Ion against Square of Number of Moles in one litre of Aqueous Organic Solvent: (1) aqueous acetone (O), (2) aqueous dioxane (X), (3) aqueous ethanol (Δ), and (4) aqueous methanol (\bullet).

solvent, the modified water cluster consists of some organic solvent molecules. When hydrogen or hydroxyl ions enter the cluster, they displace the organic solvent molecules so that the water clusters containing H^+ or OH^- ions do not have any organic molecules around them. That is the solvation sheath around H^+ and OH^- ions is made up entirely of water molecules.

The K^+ , Na^+ and Cl^- ions are highly solvated and in aqueous organic solvent the nearest layer in which the ion enters consists entirely of water due to the displacement of the organic molecule by the ion. The other clusters retain the organic molecules. So that the solvation sheath contains both water and organic molecules but the solvent molecules immediately in the neighbourhood of the ion are water molecules.

The solvation sheath has a profound effect on the conductivity of ions. The dielectric constant of the medium which is the capacity to weaken the force of attraction between the electrically charged particles in solution is one of the important factors influencing the electrical conductivity. However,

Fig. 5 : Plot of Equivalent Conductivity of Chloride Ion against Square of Number of Moles in one litre of Aqueous Organic Solvent: (1) aqueous acetone (O), (2) aqueous dioxane (X), (3) aqueous ethanol (Δ), and (4) aqueous methanol (\bullet).

effective dielectric around the ions is not given by the dielectric constant of the bulk of the mixed solvent but is determined by the solvation sheath around the ion. The solvent molecules in the neighbourhood of the ions are water molecules and as a rule conductivity of the ions diminishes with the decrease in the water content of the solvent medium.

Equivalent conductivity is obtained from the specific conductivity by multiplying with the volume in millilitres containing one gram equivalent of the electrolyte. The concentration here is expressed on weight volume basis. This can more appropriately be expressed in molar composition. In aqueous solution, the values of equivalent conductivity calculated from the specific conductivity when concentration is expressed either in weight volume basis or in molar composition do not differ. But in aqueous organic solvents, the total number of moles in one litre of the solvent mixture

goes on diminishing as the water is replaced increasingly by the organic solvent. The electrolyte behaves as if the ionic concentration is enhanced. The enhanced concentration factor is inversely proportional to N , the total number of moles in the solvent mixture.

Viscosity of solvent medium is another factor that affects electrical conductivity. It primarily influences the mobility of the ions. The most acceptable structure of hydrogen ion is represented by H^+4H_2O or $H_9O_4^+$ ¹⁷. Hydrogen and hydroxyl ions and water molecule have same electronic structure and possibly the ions can enter or come out of the water cluster as easily as the water molecules themselves¹⁸. The transference of hydrogen or hydroxyl ion, therefore, will involve only proton transfer as postulated in Grotthuss mechanism and this is not subjected to any resistance from the viscous polymeric species in the mixed solvent. The high viscosity due to the formation of the polymeric species^{9,10} therefore need not influence the mobility of hydrogen or hydroxyl ions. Sodium, potassium and chloride ions also are highly solvated. The clustered structures in mixed solvent may not therefore influence the conductance of these ions also. Thus the ionic conductivity is not influenced by the enhanced viscosity due to the polymeric species formed in the mixed solvent. However, it is affected by the normal alteration in the viscosity due to the replacement of water in the solvent mixture with the increasing proportion of the organic solvent.

An interesting observation is made from the graph obtained by plotting the viscosity of pure solvents (water, methanol, ethanol, acetone and dioxane) against N , the number of solvent moles in one litre of these liquids (Fig. 6). The points corresponding to methanol and acetone fall on the line and the points corresponding to water are somewhat outside the line. The points showing ethanol and dioxane are also away from the graph. Evidently viscosity of the liquids, acetone and methanol, in which molecules are not in associated condition is proportional to N . And viscosity of other liquids because of association of molecules and other reasons, is not proportional to N . For the purpose of correlation between the conductivity and viscosity, it is assumed here that (1) conductivity is proportional to viscosity of liquid in monomeric condition, (2) viscosity of monomers, that is of the unassociated molecules in liquid solvents, is proportional to N and (3) according to additivity law, viscosity of the hypothetical monomers in aqueous organic solvent is proportional to the sum of the number of moles of water and organic solvent in the mixture.

The combined influence of the concentration and the viscosity terms is that the conductivity goes on diminishing proportionately to N^2 in aqueous

Fig. 6 : Plot of Viscosity in Poise $\times 10^{-3}$ against Number of Moles in one litre of pure solvent.

organic solvents. The conductivity - N^2 relation is obeyed in the case of all the five ions in water-ethanol and water-dioxane. The relation is obeyed in the case of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions in water-methanol and water-acetone, but the compliance with the linear relationship of conductivity values with N^2 is not observed in high organic solvent mixtures of water-methanol and water-acetone systems in the case of other ions (Na^+ , K^+ and Cl^-). The relation is obeyed up to 50 : 50 composition of these solvent mixtures and the conductivity values remain more or less constant in the composition range of the high organic solvent mixture.

Presumably the diminution in the conductivity values with the increase in the organic component in the mixed solvent continues up to the stage the equivalent conductivity of the ion in the mixture is equal to that in the pure organic solvent. Apparently the conductivity values for Na^+ , K^+ and Cl^- in the water-methanol and water-acetone mixtures (50 : 50 composition) are equal to those in pure methanol or acetone and therefore there is no change in the conductivity values in the high organic mixtures. In other cases the linear relationship is observed in all cases as the conductivity in the mixtures exceeds that in the pure organic solvents. Although some values in methanol and ethanol solutions at 25° are reported in literature which corroborate this statement, conductivity data at 30° are required to confirm the finding.

The solvent medium is an important factor which influences the industrial processes. The above study gives insight into the electrical properties of the mixed solvent systems which are coming into use more and more in modern chemical industry.

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